

GREAT Case Study

Waterwise: Exploratory Sustainable Game Jam – EPIC -WE Collaboration

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Case Study Lead: UoB

Author(s): Paul Watson (p.watson@greatermanchester.ac.uk)

Point of Contact: Hendrik Drachsler

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List of Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DI	Digital Innovation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EGE	The European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
GREAT	Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
UKRI	United Kingdom Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

Objective: This report examines the findings of a collaboration between the GREAT and EPIC-WE projects. The primary goal of this case study was to evaluate the use of EPIC-WE game jams as a playful dissemination and community engagement tool within the GREAT project. Specifically, the study aimed to determine if game making could deepen participant reflection, help citizens make sense of complex social dilemmas such as water security, and identify the benefits and risks to citizens.

Methods: This research utilised a mixed qualitative, non-experimental design involving two distinct student cohorts from the University of Greater Manchester who participated in an adapted version of the EPIC-WE game jam toolkit. The methodology integrated playful discussion activities from the GSC2 GREAT project case study to inspire the "Water Security" theme for the game jam. Data was systematically collected through repeated-measures surveys to track shifts in self reported household water use. Structured observations of group dynamics, appraisals of final game designs to extract thematic messages, and semi-structured interviews were used to explore participant intentions and skill development.

Key Findings: The findings indicate that while game jams are a powerful engagement tool, thematic exploration varied considerably: some participants integrated serious social dilemmas into their mechanics, others prioritised gameplay and entertainment over the core message. Participants reported individual reductions in water use and increased awareness of wasteful habits, although these individual changes were not evident at the group level. The process fostered significant upskilling in teamwork, critical thinking, and design, yet it also introduced stress and the risk of simplifying complex issues due to the high cognitive demands of the task. Additionally, the activities proved effective in challenging cultural assumptions, such as the belief that water is an infinite resource.

Implications: There is a need to build a shared water culture in the UK to combat apathy and ensure that individual actions are seen as part of a collective effort involving government and industry. To combat apathy to individual impact of water use, it is recommended to find avenues that explain how government, industry and citizens are changing habits and policy, so all are moving towards the same water use vision. Importantly to citizens, policy should focus on providing localised data of individual water use profiles with collective data that help users interpret their consumption within a broader supply context. Future research into the use of game jams for dissemination and engagement with social dilemmas should balance creative autonomy with structure to reduce cognitive load. There is potential for using game jam artefacts as prototypes for more polished, professional tools for public outreach.

2. Introduction

As part of the GCS2 (waterwise) case study, the research team collaborated with an EU-funded sister project, EPIC-WE (Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments) (EPIC-WE, 2025) to extend the use of GREAT qualitative playful discussion activities in a cultural game jam. A game jam is an intensive, time-bounded event (typically one to three days) where teams or individuals attempt to make a complete game within a given theme. EPIC-WE is exploring how young people can engage with and shape European culture and values through game making. Across several sites, EPIC-WE has developed a game jam toolkit that scaffolds the game jam and focuses on engaging participants with culture and heritage to inspire the games made. Game making thus serves as both an individual and collective engagement with cultural subject matter. The GREAT project utilises playful activities to foster small group discussion on important climate conversations and policy implications. The GREAT project can potentially leverage its discussion activities as inspiration for game making applying the EPIC-WE toolkit (Nørgård & Holflod, 2024). This would help provide outreach for the GREAT activities in a different context and present an opportunity to see if game making can deepen participant reflection, attitudes, and sensemaking upon these GREAT discussion topics.

Game making invites people to grapple with complex ideas by requiring them to interpret cultural, ethical, and historical concepts and express those interpretations through interactive systems. Costa et al. (2024) argue that this process deepens engagement because understanding develops within collaborative creation: participants externalise their assumptions, test them through design choices, and revise them as their ideas take shape. Rather than treating concepts as fixed content to be learned, designers work with them as creative materials, crafting mechanics and narratives that articulate their own readings of a theme. Studies of serious game jams demonstrate that thematic constraints push young creators to reason through social and cultural issues as part of their creative problem-solving (Aibara, Kawakami & Furuichi, 2022). Work on global game jams similarly highlights how iterative prototyping and group discussion foster sustained reflection on the ideas being explored (Arya, Chastine, Preston & Fowler, 2013).

A researcher from the GREAT project observed one of the EPIC-WE game jams in September 2025 to support collaboration between the projects. This visit provided an opportunity to see the toolkit in use and to discuss shared approaches. A working group with representatives from both projects was then established to identify points of contact for when the GREAT project would use the game jam toolkit, review findings, and collaborate on publications arising from this work.

Within the GREAT project, this work is considered as an exploratory dissemination activity. In the GREAT case study cycle, it aligns with step seven, community engagement (Hollins, 2024). By integrating a game jam format, the project outreaches the GCS2 playful discussion activities to a wider audience. This may engage individuals who would not typically participate in the GCS2 activities but are more likely to do so within a game-based event. From this perspective, this exploratory study serves as an opportunity to trial and evaluate new dissemination activities for the GREAT project cycle and the impact on those that take part.

Research Questions

Through this collaboration, we focused on three GREAT project research questions to frame our exploration:

RQ 1.1 Which games-based activities can be used to elicit, represent and communicate citizens' views on social dilemmas?

- **Does game making help or hinder climate related discussions:** Game making within a game jam context is intensive, collaborative, and rewarding problem solving. This may give opportunity and time to reflect on a GREAT discussion, and collaboratively make sense of climate impact, policy evaluations, and individual responsibility. Or does the act of making games shift focus from these opportunities for the pragmatic need of making a game in a short timespan.

RQ 1.4 How widely applicable are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas, and which variables need to be taken into consideration when adapting them to different contexts?

- **Games with serious messages:** Can the games made express key ideas from the GREAT playful discussion activities. Do these games enable further dissemination of key thoughts, values, and priorities for others to engage with.

RQ 2.3 What are the benefits and risks to citizens of using games-based activities to elicit, represent and communicate their views on social dilemmas?

- **Game jams for skill growth:** The problem-solving collaborative nature of game jams requires many critical thinking, design, and teamwork skills. When taking part in a game jam, do participants feel that they make progress in these areas. What is difficult for participants and what are the rewards?

This document reports on two distinct student cohorts within the university of Greater Manchester that took part in a GREAT game jam which applied the EPIC-WE game jam toolkit. The theme was guided by GCS2 playful discussion activities.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

Given the exploratory nature of this investigation, the research design used mixed qualitative methods. The overarching approach was non-experimental seeking to qualitatively examine participants experience and perceptions for taking part in the game jam. The study incorporated repeated measures, surveying participants on their water use and perceptions before the discussion activities (Watson, 2025) and one week later. This was to explore the impact of theme on participant water use behaviour.

EPIC-WE game jam Overview

Figure 1 gives an overview of the EPIC-WE cultural game jam approach. There are four phases to guide the design process and team forming. At each phase there are aims to achieve, processes to achieve these aims, outcomes based on these processes, and a transition tool that concludes the phase and bridges to the next.

Experience phase: Participants explore games, game design, and the jam's cultural or value-based theme through exhibitions, stories, and environmental activities. Groups form, reflect on the theme, and outline initial directions.

Play phase: Teams freely generate and share ideas, building rough prototypes. Experts provide early feedback to refine concepts and highlight opportunities or issues.

Imagine phase: Groups commit to a direction and develop a playable version. Iteration, playtesting, and feedback lead to substantial design refinement.

Create phase: The selected idea moves into full production, shaping games into a public-ready prototype for exhibition and online sharing.

Phase	Experience	Play	Imagine	Create
Aims	Experience games, culture, and values	Play with concepts of games, culture, and values	Imagine games, culture, and values	Create games, culture, and values
Process	Introduce/Evoke, Team-up, Define/Decide	Brainstorm, tinker, conceptualise ideas	Iterate, prototype towards a finalised idea	Iterate, refine game / culture. Document + present work
Outcome	Game / Culture elements	Game + Culture concepts + Mock-Ups	Playable Prototype, Concept Art	Game for culture
Transition Tool	Ideation Cubes, Wheel	Hub Council	Playtest Game	Game for culture / Expo

Figure 1. Overview of the EPIC-WE game jam methodology adapted from Nørgård & Høflod (2024). The four phases describe the expected design process. The aims highlight goals of each stage while the process and outcome describe expected tasks and artefacts created at each stage. The transition tools bring groups through to the next phase of the design process.

Adaptations from EPIC-WE Toolkit

Game jams can be completed across various timeframes. Normally they span from a day through to a week. The adapted EPIC-We toolkit utilised three contact points to align with our research goals and participant logistics (See Figure 2). Contact point one was used for the Experience phase whereby the GREAT GCS2 playful activities (Watson, 2025) were used to spark discussion and reflection on water use in the home and how citizen water behaviour could be adjusted and supported to waste less water. This inspired the theme of “Water Security” to direct game design. Contact point two embraced the play phase entirely. Contact point three combined the Imagine and Create phases. Due to logistics, we did not have a final expo for the developed games and expected sufficient development of game ideas to occur by the end of the Imagine phase. This approach engaged minimally with the Create phase but used small prizes for the games made to celebrate the end of the game jam.

Phase / Contact Point	Experience / 1	Play / 2	Imagine / 3	Create / 3
Aims	Experience games + GREAT water security activities	Play with game concepts + water security theming	Create prototype of chosen idea for playtest	Refine for submission
Process	Introduce/Evoke, Team-up, Define/Decide	Brainstorm, tinker, conceptualise ideas	Iterate, prototype towards a finalised idea	Use playtesting to refine final design
Outcome	Game ideas + water security theme representation	Written development log that captures ideas and feedback	Playbale Prototype, Concept Art	Refined prototype
Transition Tool	Group discussions on ideas, sketches + feedback	Hub Council to feedback on ideas	Playtest Game and describe how it is connected to theme	Submit game and rulesheet, conclude and give prizes

Figure 2. Adapted EPIC-WE game jam methodology across three participant contact points. Owing to logistical constraints, engagement with the “create” phase was limited. The “experience” phase drew on playful activities developed in GREAT to introduce participants to the theme.

For cohort one, the contact points occurred across three weeks with one contact point each week. For cohort two, the three contact points were across 1 week.

3.2 Participant selection

Two cohorts were used. Both were a convenience sample of students studying on Computer Science Masters degree and Games degree at the University of Greater Manchester. Students were selected because participation would complement their research studies and design skillsets. Using student cohorts enabled controlled contact points across several days that would have been impractical outside of class time. Due to the sampling bias of a convenience sample, two cohorts were chosen with distinct characteristics (see table 1) of different study levels, nationality, age, course discipline, gender mix, and game making experience. Students were informed of how taking part compliments their studies and told that they would be given a different assignment if they did not wish to take part. An information sheet on all scheduled activities was provided and each class given time to discuss before consent was obtained. It was emphasised that students can withdraw at any time during the study. Student workload was monitored to ensure reasonable time commitments. Due to the different game making background of the student cohorts, the Computer Science students were required to make a non-

digital game (board game, card game) while the Games students were required to make a digital game to express their design.

Table 1. This table describes participant demographic information of the two cohorts that took part in the game jams

Demographics	Cohort 1	Cohort 2
N	29	28
Age	Average = 34, min = 25, max = 44	Average = 23, min = 20, Max = 50
Male/Female	16/13	25/3
Nationality	Pakistan = 3, UK = 1, Nigeria = 25	UK = 26, Hong Kong = 2
When	October 2025	December 2025

3.3 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained through the University of Greater Manchester Ethics board (approval number: MANUP00340). Discussions took place with module leaders to make sure game jam content and workload complimented student studies and commitments. Students were given the opportunity for a different activity if they did not want to take part in the game jam or take part without having their data collected. The right to withdraw at any time was emphasised. The schedule of events was given in an information sheet during class with time to discuss any details. Students were informed that their email would be collected to connect data observations, but this information will be destroyed at the end of the project. All interviews would be transcribed and anonymised before analysis with original recordings being destroyed at the end of the project.

3.4 Data Collection Methods

Instruments

GREAT GCS2 activity responses: A survey on participants' household water use was administered as Activity 1 in the GCS2 sequence and again one week later, following the repeated-measures approach used in previous GCS2 work (Watson, 2025). Comparing these self-reported measures helped indicate whether the water sustainability discussions and game-making based on this theme influenced participants' personal water use behaviours

Game Jam Activity Observations: Observations during facilitation were guided by a structured rubric to capture activity flow, use of space, participant engagement, barriers, class

dynamics, and signs of empowered participation. These insights helped assess how effectively the activities supported information sharing, discussion, and idea development.

Final Game Designs: At the end of the game jam teams submitted their game and any supporting material like a rule sheet. These were evaluated for messages associated to the theme and what type of game design was used. This appraisal examined the extent messages around the game jam theme had been developed and how instruction on game design might have influenced final design choices.

Interviews: At the end of the game jam, team interviews explored each group's game design, expected player responses, key design influences, experiences of participating in the game jam, and perceptions of any skills or knowledge gained. These conversations allowed participants to articulate their intentions, reflect on sources of inspiration, and consider the personal impact of the process.

Rationale of Instruments

We are exploring how taking part in a game jam inspired by GREAT project playful discussions can:

- Engage citizens with water sustainability
- Be a vehicle to express own water sustainability messages
- Impact on perceived skillset

The study employed four data collection instruments, each addressing specific research objectives. Survey responses enabled assessment of water use behaviours before the start of the game jam and one week later. Through interviews we can explore further the extent to which any behaviour changes have been noticed. Game jam activity observations will help report on the extent to which these cohorts took part in these discussions and engagement with the activities. Evaluating final game designs can give insights to the types of messages participants feels are important within the theme. Interviews will be used to explore game design and theme influences to help build this picture and how the act of game making may mediate the types of messages participants are able to present. Through interviews we will explore participant perception of impact on individual skillsets, key challenges experienced, and perceived victories during the game jam. This will give insight into using game jams in this context in terms of benefits and risks to citizens.

3.5 Mapping of RQ's to Case Study

Table 2. Mapping of research questions to the case study

Revised research objectives and questions	Simple formulation in terms of GREAT	Yes/No
RQ1. To understand how games-based activities can be designed to provide a link between citizens and policy makers.		
RQ1.1 Which games-based activities can be used to elicit, represent and communicate citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>How can GREAT be achieved?</i>	YES
RQ1.2 How effective are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>Does GREAT do what we want it to do?</i>	NO
RQ1.3 How efficient is the use of games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>How much work is it to use the GREAT approach?</i>	NO
RQ1.4 How widely applicable are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas, and which variables need to be taken into consideration when adapting them to different contexts?	<i>How widely applicable is what we do?</i>	YES
RQ2. To understand the benefits and risks to citizens, policy stakeholders and policy makers, of using games-based activities as a link between citizens and policy makers.		
RQ2.1 What are the affordances of games in eliciting and representing citizens' views in relation to social dilemmas.	<i>What is it about GREAT that makes it good for gathering and representing opinions and attitudes?</i>	NO

RQ2.2 What are the benefits and risks to policy makers and policy stakeholders of using games-based activities to elicit, represent and communicate citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>What is good and bad about GREAT for policy stakeholders and policy makers?</i>	NO
RQ2.3 What are the benefits and risks to citizens of using games-based activities to elicit, represent and communicate their views on social dilemmas?	<i>What is good and bad about GREAT for citizens?</i>	YES

4. SWOT Analysis of Case Study Methodology

Table 3. SWOT Analysis of Case Study Methodology

Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>As a dissemination activity, the game jam showed strong potential for engaging people in a social dilemma discussion.</p> <p>It offered a rewarding way to build teamwork, game-making skills, creative software confidence, and a sense of achievement.</p> <p>When teams worked well, the experience was especially positive.</p> <p>The range of final game concepts demonstrated how differently water supply and demand challenges can be framed and communicated to wider audiences.</p>	<p>Game jams demand substantial time and energy. Integrating them into everyday public routines would require strong logistical and facilitation support.</p> <p>Larger groups may also foster distraction during sustainability discussions, making it harder for all participants to contribute meaningfully.</p> <p>When teams struggle to collaborate, the experience can become stressful and discouraging.</p> <p>Limited development time also means promising game ideas cannot be refined for wider public use, and strong concepts may not reach their full potential.</p>
Opportunities	Threats
<p>More focused prompts on social dilemmas and game design could make it easier for participants to handle both elements at once.</p> <p>Marking the end of the jam with a celebration creates an engaging and motivating conclusion.</p>	<p>Game jams demand considerable time from both participants and organisers, which can restrict when and how they are used.</p>

<p>Game jam format may be especially well suited to conferences or holiday events.</p> <p>There is also scope to produce non-game artefacts that still engage meaningfully with the DiBL social dilemma.</p> <p>Game concepts developed during the jam could support wider public outreach, but they need additional time and resources to mature. Securing mechanisms to develop these ideas further would help strong concepts reach broader audiences and inform future research.</p>	<p>Supporting them with social dilemma content also requires bespoke activity design, potentially limiting opportunities to run them at scale.</p> <p>More broadly, game creation itself is a time and talent intensive process. Participant energy and expectations need to be managed well.</p>
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5. Key Findings

RQ 1.1 Which games-based activities can be used to elicit, represent and communicate citizens' views on social dilemmas?

This case study examined the use of GCS2 playful discussion activities to inspire game making for a game jam. This would give participants opportunity to engage with the water security topic within these discussions and during the process of making a game. Expression of views was expected to surface in three ways:

1. Discussion content recorded during GCS2 activities
2. Changes in water behaviour during the game jam
3. Messages of fair water use within game made

Discussion content recorded during GCS2 activities

Across both cohorts, the GSC2 discussion activities surfaced a wide range of perspectives and assumptions about fair water use. Some participants expressed conspiratorial beliefs that the water crisis is manufactured, while others argued that water is so abundant that personal management is unnecessary and supply should simply be increased. Many were surprised when confronted with their own levels of water use.

The discussion format encouraged critical questioning and the sharing of contrasting viewpoints. The playful dilemma created space for debate about how citizen water use should be managed, allowing participants to move between serious and light hearted engagement. At

the same time, there were signs of groupthink, with clusters of participants converging on similar responses but without depth of explanation.

Changes in water behaviour during the game jam

A self-report water use survey was completed at the start of the game jam and again one week later. Some participants reported reduced water use in the follow-up survey, often noting that they had made a conscious effort to cut back in areas they felt were excessive. This indicates that individuals can recognise and reflect on previously wasteful habits. However, across both cohorts the overall reduction in water use was only marginal, suggesting that most participants did not feel a strong need to change their behaviour at a group level. This pattern implies that the discussion activities used to prompt game jam ideas may help individuals identify specific areas of overuse and report small, manageable adjustments. In contrast, habits that require greater effort or more substantial lifestyle changes were not expressed.

The surveys were able to generate distinct water use profiles for individuals. Cohort 1 reported significantly lower water use than Cohort 2, and they were also more willing to report making changes to their water use habits, despite already using less water overall. The two cohorts differed demographically in terms of average age, subject area, gender mix, and nationality. These differences suggest that the survey approach can capture water use profiles that help interpret participants' views and reveal how demographic context may shape or interact with those profiles

Messages of fair water use within game made

Across the two cohorts, approaches to the theme of water security differed noticeably. Many of the games created in Cohort 1 actively engaged players with a water security social dilemma. These games often asked players to balance limited water resources with everyday lifestyle decisions, or to focus on maintaining water infrastructure within the home. The underlying aim was to increase awareness of how water is used and how local supply can be sustained. Both the games and the accompanying interviews suggest that helping people understand their daily water use can empower them to make more informed choices.

Cohort 2, by contrast, was often split between simply wanting to make an enjoyable game and wanting to communicate a message about water use. Some teams deliberately designed games that taught players about fair water use and reducing waste. Others explored speculative narratives, imagining worlds where water supplies had drastically diminished and examining how such societies might function or survive. In interviews, however, Cohort 2 participants more frequently explained that water security messaging was not their main priority. Creating a fun game took precedence.

In summary, the game jam provided multiple points at which participants expressed their attitudes and preferences regarding fair water use. For some, the game jam process encouraged further enquiry as they researched ideas to inform their game concepts. Others, however, ended their exploration after the GCS2 discussions and shifted their attention primarily to creating an entertaining game. Without additional elements such as post-jam interviews, it would be difficult to trace how participants engaged with the theme solely from the final game artefact. Improvements to the specificity of the theme may help engage more participants to express their social dilemma attitudes and preferences within the game artefact.

RQ 1.4 How widely applicable are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens’ views on social dilemmas, and which variables need to be taken into consideration when adapting them to different contexts?

Using the GCS2 activities to inspire a game jam represents a diverse use of these activities. The addition of game making encouraged some students to engage more deeply with water security social dilemmas, giving them additional time to research and to consider how to communicate their ideas through a playable experience. Interview data shows that several participants felt they needed to explore water security issues beyond the initial GCS2 discussions in order to develop a meaningful game concept. Post-jam interviews also indicate that taking part in the game jam contributed to some shifts in behaviour and beliefs.

During the GCS2 discussions, participants in Cohort 1 expressed an initial belief that water supply is abundant and therefore does not require active management. Many of these students, predominantly Nigerian nationals, framed this through a cultural perspective that “water is God’s gift,” implying that water is inherently free and plentiful. However, through the process of creating a game, several participants reported realising that this assumption does not hold in all contexts, and that reasonable efforts should be made to conserve water. Some also described adjusting their own and their families’ habits, such as being more mindful about leaving taps running. This transition highlights where initial beliefs on water start and where they can be more easily nudged to with support, and important element of policy design water sustainability support mechanisms.

In contrast, Cohort 2, composed of game-design students, were more likely to prioritise the act of making a game over further engagement with the water security theme. Although some of their games aligned closely with the topic, interviews suggest that most of their learning about water security came from the GCS2 activities rather than from the game making process itself.

This contrast highlights how a game jam can both support and limit deeper engagement with social dilemmas. The cognitive demands and creative focus required to produce a game can

become the primary concern, potentially diverting attention away from the thematic exploration for those who might otherwise have pursued it further.

These findings suggest that game making can complement the exploration of social dilemmas, but the complexity of the task needs careful consideration. Reducing the design complexity and making the theme more explicit may encourage greater engagement with the underlying issue. For example, providing a defined game structure and focusing on a specific water security challenge (supported by information representing different sides of the debate) could help participants concentrate more directly on the social dilemma. However, this approach risks limiting the creative freedom that some participants value and may influence their motivation to take part. Balancing structure with autonomy remains an important design consideration.

RQ 2.3 What are the benefits and risks to citizens of using games-based activities to elicit, represent and communicate their views on social dilemmas?

Engagement with the social dilemma through the game jam appeared to influence some participants' behaviour and attitudes. Observations and interviews highlighted increased concern about personal action within the dilemma, with several participants reporting changes to their water use habits at home. In attempting to design games that communicated messages about individual water use, participants were also prompted to reflect on their own impact. Although behaviour change was not evident at a group level, individual accounts in interviews and self-reported survey data indicate small shifts in awareness and practice. These changes tended to occur in areas perceived as excessive or easy to modify, such as turning off taps when not in use or reducing shower time. There was little evidence that this concern extended into wider conversations about water use or other social dilemmas, suggesting that the effect remained largely contained to the individuals directly involved. The act of taking part in social dilemmas and making games within that theme may benefit citizen knowledge and understanding of their own impact within it.

Beyond engagement with the social dilemma itself, the act of making a game was experienced as intensive and demanding. Many participants described the collaborative environment as a space where they strengthened their teamwork skills and developed stronger connections with peers. Groups that functioned well reported building good rapport and felt that the challenge of creating a game enhanced their ability to think critically, listen to others, and compromise. However, when teams struggled, whether due to uneven levels of effort or poor coordination, the process became stressful and lacked the sense of reward experienced by others. Such negative experiences may be difficult to eliminate entirely but should be considered when designing similar activities.

Across a game jam, the act of making a game can both support and limit sensemaking around social dilemmas. The intense focus required to design and build a game may draw attention away from deeper engagement with the dilemma or lead some participants to set the theme aside entirely. The challenge of translating complex ideas into game mechanics can also result in simplified messages, reducing the depth of exploration as participants gravitate toward concepts that are easier to represent in play. However, it is important to recognise that even small steps toward engagement are still meaningful. While the potential for deeper exploration may be greater than what participants ultimately pursue, the moments where individuals do reflect, question, or adjust their thinking still represent progress, regardless of whether others choose to disengage.

Many participants described the moment when their game “came to life” as particularly meaningful. Those with no prior experience of game development expressed excitement and increased confidence in their ability to take on design challenges. Even participants familiar with game jams reported that seeing the final product come together remained a special moment. This suggests that the intensity and creative focus of the activity can generate highly positive and motivating experiences that can be described and remembered as triumphant.

6. Policy Implications and Recommendations

As in previous GCS2 work, discussions and game design activities highlighted the importance of giving individuals better knowledge of their water use and practical alternatives for reducing excessive consumption. This suggests that supportive mechanisms should help citizens understand their own water use and show how it compares with local groups or recommended targets. This aligns with the growing interest in SMART meters in UK households (Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs, 2026). The findings suggest potential value in enhancing SMART meter utility by pairing them with an app that helps people interpret their water use within their supply limits and local context. Within this framing water profiles could be linked to playful app activities and gamified goals to engage users with their water use and understanding of the broader water supply and demand system.

The work also points to the need to develop a stronger water culture in the UK. Younger students appeared less concerned about water use and tended to use significantly more water in their weekly household routines. When combined with media reports suggesting that water companies are not doing enough to support water efficiency and instead focus on shareholders, some citizens become less convinced that individual action matters, particularly when they feel that large companies are not contributing fairly. In this context, communications should help build a shared culture around water. They should set out a clear vision of what sustainable water

use looks like and show how government, industry and the public are working towards that vision.

As in earlier GCS2 work, simple behavioural nudges remain effective. These include turning taps off at key moments and reducing excessive habits such as very long showers. Mechanisms that encourage people to engage with these everyday actions, along with guidance on maintaining local water infrastructure, represent some of the most achievable changes that citizens can support.

6. Recommendations For Future Research:

Game jams typically generate a variety of interactive artefacts that respond to a shared theme or idea. Prior research shows that the process of creating these artefacts can strengthen participants' game development skills, support more effective collaboration, and encourage engagement with the theme itself (Meriläinen et al., 2020; Silveri, 2023). Through this thematic engagement, it is argued that game jams may also prompt individual or collective civic engagement with social issues.

This case study reinforces existing findings that participants perceive game jams as opportunities to develop both technical and collaborative design skills. However, the degree to which participants engage with them, either individually or collectively, remains less well understood. While studies suggest that participants may gain topic awareness and feel more knowledgeable (Preston, 2014; Myers, Piccolo & Collins, 2019), there is limited evidence that such experiences lead to behaviour change or reveal how deeply the theme is internalised. In this case study, a minority of participants reported some changes in water use habits and articulated reflections on these behaviours. Yet when developing their games, participants tended to prioritise artefact creation over deeper exploration of the theme (Di Staso et al., 2024).

To strengthen theme engagement in future game jam formats, best practice should investigate the following lines of enquiry:

- **Separate the design from the making:** Future game jam research may need to distinguish more clearly between the design phase and the making phase to understand how learning and civic engagement emerge across a jam. Theme exploration may occur primarily during early ideation, with limited opportunities to consolidate or extend this thinking once production pressures intensify. Comparative studies that examine participants' learning and thematic engagement during design versus making would help clarify how each stage contributes to the wider educational and civic aims of game jams.

- **Manage cognitive load to enable theme exploration:** Research should investigate how to manage the cognitive load associated with the many challenges of game creation. Refining the game jam format by narrowing the theme to a specific aspect of a social dilemma and propose a specific design template, may reduce complexity while deepening engagement with the subject matter. This approach could support more meaningful sensemaking, encourage the creation of games that reflect participants' reasoning, and produce artefacts that communicate attitudes and preferences within a social dilemma.
- **Evaluate impact through objective behaviour observations:** Further research should focus on themes that map more directly onto observable actions and everyday practice for a given cohort. For example, study habits, maintaining a professional workspace, or recycling behaviours within a controlled environment. While these topics may not align directly with broader societal priorities, they offer a clearer basis for evaluating how a game jam's theme influences subsequent behaviour and thus inform good practice.
- **Cyclical content from game jams:** The core concepts behind many of the games produced in these GCS2 exploratory game jams were both engaging and original. However, the time needed to develop these games to a high standard is likely to exceed what is normally achievable within a game jam. One possible solution is to use the games created in a jam as inspiration for future game jams, or to involve groups who are interested in developing the ideas further. This could provide more polished artefacts that connect the public with messages within games and observe any influence on player behaviour and understanding of social dilemmas.

7. Conclusion

This case study demonstrates that games jam activities can elicit, represent and communicate citizens' views on social dilemmas, though the depth of engagement varies across participants and stages of the process. The GCS2 discussions encouraged a broad range of perspectives on fair water use and prompted reflection, while self reported surveys showed willingness to make small, manageable adjustments rather than substantial behaviour change across the cohorts. The games produced during the jam revealed that some participants used the medium to explore water security dilemmas, whereas others focused primarily on creating an enjoyable experience.

The wider findings suggest that the applicability of games based methods depends heavily on context, participant background and the structure of the activity. When combined with GCS2 discussions, game making supported deeper engagement for some participants, particularly

those who reconsidered cultural assumptions about water abundance and reported small shifts in personal habits. At the same time, the cognitive demands of game production can limit thematic exploration, especially for participants who prioritise creative or technical goals.

Participation in game jams may benefit individuals with increased awareness of individual roles within a social dilemma and opportunities for collaborative learning and confidence building. However, they also carry risks, such as stress, uneven group experiences and simplified representations of complex issues. Engagement may remain individual rather than extending into wider conversations or sustained change.

Overall, game jam approaches offer a nuanced way to explore social dilemmas. They can prompt meaningful reflection and generate creative artefacts that communicate citizen perspectives, yet their effectiveness depends on careful design choices that balance thematic focus with participants' creative autonomy.

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